

Assessing the Feasibility of Deep Lagrangian Networks for Industrial-Level Control of a Parallel Kinematic Machine

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Abstract. Model-based control is crucial for efficient robotic operations, yet accurately identifying robot dynamics remains challenging, particularly for parallel kinematic machines (PKMs). This work leverages physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), specifically the Deep Lagrangian Network in combination with non-symmetric Coulomb friction, to achieve physically consistent dynamic models by incorporating principles such as energy conservation and friction modeling. Validated on the ABB IRB 360-6/1600 Delta robot, the approach demonstrates high fidelity in torque prediction and effective real-time control implementation on industrial hardware under stringent computational constraints. Experimental results highlight improved torque prediction accuracy, reduced trajectory tracking lag, and robust handling of complex dynamic interactions, paving the way for adaptive and efficient industrial automation.

Keywords: PINN-model-based control, Deep Learning, Physics-Informed Neural Networks, Real-time Control, Industrial Robotics

1 Introduction

Model-based control is essential for achieving fast, accurate, and safe robotic operations. However, obtaining accurate robot models can be significantly challenging due to insufficient CAD data, difficulties in modeling and measuring non-linearities, the tedious analytical modeling process for parallel robots, and other limitations. Consequently, the development of robust model identification techniques is crucial to obtaining models that closely resemble the physical system.

Research has extensively explored various model identification methods, mostly derived from conventional least squares (LS) by exploiting the linear relationship between dynamic parameters and inverse dynamics equations. However,

these conventional approaches often fall short in achieving physically meaningful and consistent results. Techniques involving data-driven approaches, such as machine learning (ML), have seen limited application in the model identification and control of parallel kinematic manipulators (PKMs) in the literature [1–3]. Typical ML techniques, which often rely on deep learning (DL) architectures, excel in torque prediction but lack physical interpretability [4], making them unsuitable for model-based controllers such as computed torque control or passivity-based control. Nonetheless, the performance of ML algorithms can be enhanced by integrating physics-based principles into DL architectures.

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), such as Deep Lagrangian Networks (DeLaN), have demonstrated the feasibility of achieving physically plausible dynamic identification by incorporating concepts such as energy conservation and friction models [5, 6]. In particular, the DeLaN architecture can infer parameters of viscous, Stribeck, and Coulomb friction. Additionally, more complex friction models, such as non-symmetrical Coulomb friction (NSCF), which depend on the direction of the angular velocity of each joint, can be included in the DeLaN architecture, thanks to DeLaN+NSCF [10]. On top of that, DeLaN+NSCF has not only demonstrated the capability to identify highly complex friction models and the lumped inertia of motor drives in a 6-degree-of-freedom (dof) serial manipulator but has also shown its applicability in modeling a Delta-like PKM [11] by incorporating kinematic priors [8]. However, while the methodology for controlling serial manipulators using insights from DeLaN+NSCF has already been explored for robots with a closed control architecture [7], it has yet to be applied to a parallel robot.

This paper introduces and develops PINN-based techniques for model-based control in industrial-grade PKM controllers. Emphasis is placed on ensuring real-time control performance and achieving the fastest possible cycle times for industrial controllers. By demonstrating the practicality of this approach in industrial settings, this work paves the way for adaptive controllers that can effectively respond to evolving dynamics and constraints.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the dynamics of PKM identification, while Section 3 discusses the required preparations for dynamic-based control. Experimental tests, including the generation of time-optimal trajectories and their execution results, are presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes with a discussion of the results and outlines future research directions.

2 Dynamics Model

In order to identify the robot dynamics of the Delta PKM ABB IRB360 (Fig. 1) using a PINN, we follow the DeLaN+NSCF methodology provided in [8]. This approach has been validated for dynamics identification in fully actuated 6-DOF serial kinematic mechanisms [10], PKMs [8], and under-actuated mechanisms [6].

The DeLaN+NSCF method leverages a neural network architecture, specifically a multilayer perceptron (MLP), to predict the diagonal (l_d) and lower diagonal (l_o) elements of the mass matrix, as well as the potential energy (V)

Fig. 1: The ABB IRB 360-6/1600 Delta robot mounted upside down to the shop floor.

of the system in terms of generalized coordinates. The performance of the MLP depends on the choice of activation functions, which must be at least one-time differentiable to compute derivatives of the Lagrangian equation via the chain rule and derive the equation of motion (EOM) under the assumption of conservative forces. To extend the model to non-conservative forces such as friction, additional layers representing these effects can be integrated into the network architecture. In this study, we incorporate linear viscous and non-symmetric Coulomb friction models, allowing the network to better capture the system's actual dynamics. Additionally, rotor inertias are considered as lumped elements to further refine the accuracy of the model.

Previous validation of DeLaN+NSCF for Delta-like robots demonstrated improved performance in torque prediction by exploiting the sparsity of the mass matrix, which arises due to the decoupling between translational and rotational motions [8]. In this study, we follow a similar approach by constraining the last three lower diagonal elements of the mass matrix to zero. This simplification enables the model to leverage the decoupled nature of the Delta-like ABB IRB360 PKM, leading to improved system identification with DeLaN+NSCF.

In order to identify the dynamics of our target system, we follow the workflow depicted in Fig. 2a. The process begins with the generation of random excitation trajectories, represented as truncated Fourier series with amplitude coefficients sampled from a uniform distribution. These coefficients are scaled to ensure that the resulting trajectories remain within the physical limits of the workspace. Executing these trajectories enables efficient exploration of the task space while adhering to predefined constraints. For this study, a total of 63 trajectories were executed, yielding 2,362,500 time steps of recorded data, including joint positions and torques. Through data processing, joint velocities and accelerations are ob-

Fig. 2: (a) Graphical workflow representation of the identification process using the DeLaN+NSCF technique. (b) Software workflow implementation.

tained via filtering. The dataset is then split into training and validation sets, and inverse dynamics identification performed by training the DeLaN+NSCF model.

3 PINN-model-based feed-forward control

The implementation our DeLaN+NSCF model within an Automation PC (APC) for robot control poses significant challenges due to the stringent computational time constraints. In each cycle, the system must complete all computation tasks within a 400 μs time window, limiting the overall processing capacity. Moreover, for high-level programming languages like Python this constraint makes it practically unusable. In order to overcome this limitation, we optimized the computation time as much as possible compared to the original Python implementation by rewriting the forward run of DeLaN+NSCF in a low-level programming language, specifically C. Therefore, as depicted in depicted in Fig. 2b, from the trained model all the weights are saved, and the forward run of the DeLaN+NSCF is re-written into C language. Consequently, the C code is passed into the Simulink model of the APC, which in order to be executable in the robot, is later code generated and compiled. This workflow, outlines the sequence of operations performed after identifying the inverse dynamic model (as illustrated in Fig. 2a). DeLaN+NSCF was trained on an NVIDIA RTX3090 GPU installed on an Ubuntu PC using a set of 63 random excitation trajectories, sampled at 2.5 kHz. The dataset was then split into a training set of 48 trajectories and a validation set of 15 trajectories, and trained with attention to both training and validation loss to prevent overfitting.

The obtained weights of the DeLaN+NSCF model trained offline in Python are used by an implementation of the forward pass of the same model in C, which is finally imported into Matlab. Initially, the use of ONNX to convert the model was tested. However, this conversion resulted into different incompatible variable types to code generate using Matlab, leading to manually translate the

Fig. 3: Graphical representation of the TCP of the ABB IRB 360 robot executing the time-optimal pick-and-place motion.

code into C. By using our setup, this Matlab code is further used in a Simulink model that is finally code generated to the APC. Our aim is to find a sufficient workaround for the Python programming language, since no industrial hardware setup processes Python. As a result, we can confidently execute trajectories at a rate of 2.5 kHz on the APC.

In order to control the robot and execute the motion task, we utilize an Automation PC (APC) (5PC910.SX02-00) from Bernecker and Reiner Industrial Automation (B&R), which is powered by an Intel Core i7 6820EQ CPU. This high-performance processor enables a cycle time of 400 μ s for controlling the robot. Motion control of the drive units equipped with 15-bit absolute encoders is handled by two ACOPOS P3 servo amplifiers (8EI8X8MWT10). For the industrial controller, it is only possible to provide feed-forward torques to improve the control performance, since the cascaded PD control internal structure of the servo amplifier cannot be changed.

4 Results & Discussion

Delta robots are designed for highly dynamic pick and place tasks. Hence, a 800 mm long and 180 mm high U-turn motion along the y-axis of the inertial frame is used as example. The 90° rotation of the end-effector (EE) is omitted for simplicity. A 2.5 kg weight plate is attached to the EE. A detailed explanation of the optimization of the pick-and-place task together with the kinematics limits considered on the actuated joints, the actuation torques $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, as well as the reaction forces, is provided in [9]. The optimized motion was stored as look-up table on the real-time control unit. Figure 3 shows the EE motion, it consists of a trajectory from the home configuration to the start position, the optimized motion, and a trajectory back to the home position. The optimized motion takes roughly 0.5 s and starts at $t \approx 1.4$ s. The optimized motion was executed on the control unit

Fig. 4: Graphical representation of the torques predicted from our DeLaN+NSCF model and the measured torques of the physical ABB IRB 360-6/1600 robot.

and the set feed-forward torques τ_{FF} , the measured motor torques τ , the set joint angles \mathbf{q}_D and measured joint angles \mathbf{q} were recorded.

Figure 4 shows the recorded motor torques τ and the feed-forward torques τ_{FF} provided by the PINN. The excellent fit of the feed-forward torques for all four motors can be clearly seen. The small exaltation occurring at $t \approx 1.5$ s for τ_2 and at $t \approx 1.7$ s for τ_3 can be explained by the nonlinear friction occurring inside the prismatic joint of the telescope bar, it is assumed that a saturation effect occurs. However, the results fit very well, indicating good control performance. The better the provided feed-forward torques fit, the better the and more dynamic motions can be executed due to the precise system identification of the PINN. Moreover, from τ_4 , it is worth to mention that the PINN model successfully captured the effects of what appear to be parasitic motions in the rotation of the EE. This type of motions occur as side effect of other, primary movements [12]. Since no rotation of the EE is to be executed as seen in Fig. 3, the corresponding motor torque τ_4 was expected to be zero. These subtle parasitic motions/torques are particularly evident at $t \approx 0.8$ s and 1.6s. This can be explained by a slightly tilted rotation axis of the fourth motor and the revolute joint in the platform. Hence, it is assumed that the telescope bar required for the rotation of the EE does not completely cancel these effects with its two universal joints.

A further control performance indicator is the lag error $\Delta\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_D - \mathbf{q}$, which is shown in Fig. 5. The control setup enforces constraints to keep the lag error below 1° , guaranteeing safety during operation. An emergency stop is automatically triggered if the lag error exceeds this threshold. The small lag error with respect to the load side, with an absolute maximum of 0.4° , proves both the efficiency and sufficiency of the proposed control method using the PINN feed-forward torques while meeting the safety requirements of the robot.

Fig. 5: Graphical representation of the Lag error between the desired joint position and the actual joint position of the ABB IRB 360-6/1600 robot.

5 Conclusion

This research successfully developed and implemented the DeLaN+NSCF model for dynamic identification and torque prediction of a fully actuated PKM. This innovative approach combines the strengths of PINNs with an in-depth understanding of the underlying mechanical system to model-based control, and assesses the feasibility of using DeLaNs for Industrial-Level control of PKMs.

The effectiveness of the DeLaN+NSCF model was rigorously tested on the Delta-like ABB IRB360 PKM. The model demonstrated exceptional accuracy in predicting the dynamics of the robot, particularly in handling non-conservative forces, which are crucial for real-world scenarios. Furthermore, the implementation of the model on an APC met the stringent 400 μ s computational time requirement, proving its feasibility for real-time control applications.

The DeLaN+NSCF model holds immense potential for revolutionizing industrial automation. By enabling real-time adjustments to control strategies in response to changing environmental conditions, it enhances the adaptability and flexibility of robotic systems. It translates to optimized production processes, improved product quality, reduced energy consumption, minimized environmental impact, and enhanced overall system safety and reliability.

Future research could investigate the applicability of DeLaN+NSCF to other robotic systems, such as hybrid robots. Developing advanced control strategies that utilize the predictions of DeLaN+NSCF could further enhance performance and adaptability. Additionally, exploring the potential of DeLaN+NSCF in other domains, such as autonomous vehicles and smart manufacturing, could unlock new avenues for robotics. By continuously advancing our understanding and capabilities in data-driven dynamic identification and torque prediction, we can pave the way for more efficient, effective, and adaptive robotic systems, unlocking new possibilities across various industries.

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